

IN-PLANE AND THROUGH THICKNESS PERMEABILITY CHARACTERIZATION OF 3D WOVEN REINFORCEMENTS

Hussam Alhussein¹, Rehan Umer¹, Elinor Swery², Sanjeev Rao¹, Wesley Cantwell¹, and Simon Bickerton²

¹Aerospace Research and Innovation Center, Khalifa University, Abu Dhabi, UAE
P.O. Box 127788,

²Center for Advanced Composite Materials, The University of Auckland, New Zealand
Email: hussam.alhussein@kustar.ac.ae, web page: <http://www.kustar.ac.ae>

Keywords: 3D fabrics, Permeability, LCM

ABSTRACT

In this study, the permeability of three different 3D woven carbon fiber reinforcements (orthogonal, angle interlock and layer to layer) was studied. For all reinforcements, unsaturated radial in-plane, and saturated through-thickness permeability was obtained at several fiber volume fractions. The effect of cyclic compaction on permeability was also investigated. Orthogonal and layer to layer showed more anisotropy in the plane of flow. Angle interlock and orthogonal anisotropy ratio was approximately constant. The decrease in in-plane permeability with increasing fiber volume content was less than through thickness. The effect of cyclic compaction on permeability was greater for orthogonal and angle interlock reinforcements. Micrographs of infused samples showed significant permanent deformation of z-binder yarns which reduced permeability at high fiber volume content.

1 INTRODUCTION

Liquid composite molding (LCM) is becoming one of the major out of autoclave manufacturing processes in industries such as aerospace, automotive and marine. In this process, liquid resin is injected inside a mold containing dry compacted fibrous preforms. This process is suitable for both mass and large volume production at lower costs, compared to other composites fabrication techniques such as autoclave curing. Another very important advantage is the ability to control fiber and matrix ratio efficiently by compressing the preform to a specified thickness. The mold clamping forces and preform's viscoelastic properties depend strongly on fabric architecture or structure, the stacking sequence and mold closing speeds. LCM has many variants e.g. in vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM), the clamping force is applied using vacuum pressure under a flexible tooling. Therefore, controlling final part thickness is not straight forward as compared to resin transfer molding (RTM) process, where preform is compacted between two rigid tooling. However, VARTM is suitable for large parts where surface finish is not an issue. In both processes, the reinforcement compaction response influences the mold clamping force, mold filling and permeability. Therefore, it is vital to understand resin flow and reinforcement permeability before fabrication.

In spite of their advantage in through-thickness and inter-laminar strength and damage tolerance, fewer studies have focused on 3D fabrics. 3D woven fabrics have complex internal structure typically consisting of aligned non-crimped layers of warp and weft yarns. Moreover, a binder yarn which follows a pre-defined path holds the reinforcement together and provides stiffness and interlaminar strength to the composite. Different weave styles allow flexibility in LCM processing parameters such as compressibility and permeability. Several studies have considered mechanical properties such as stiffness and strength of 3D woven fabrics experimentally, analytically and numerically for example by Tan et al. [1, 2]. Other studies related to 2D reinforcement's permeability behaviour have received considerable attention in the past [3, 4]. Some researchers have specifically investigated radial

permeability behaviour of 2D woven, braided, stitched, and knitted preforms [5, 6]. The impregnation of liquid resin in thick 3D preforms is expected to be more complex than 2D preforms. More specifically, the z-binder fibers effectively influence both in-plane and through-thickness permeability. Only a few studies have been found on the permeability of 3D woven structures to date [7]. Endruweit et al. [7] have experimentally measured the in-plane and through thickness permeability for three different 3D woven reinforcements, where they found that the in-plane permeability values were generally in the same order of magnitude as those in 2D fabrics. In contrast, a study conducted by Mohamed et al. [8] suggested that 3D orthogonal woven fabrics have significantly higher in-plane and through thickness permeability than 2D fabrics at similar fiber volume fractions. Ngo and Tamma [9] have numerically predicted the in-plane and through thickness permeability for an orthogonal weave based on a three dimensional unit cell showing qualitative agreement with experimental observations. The simulations indicated that the in-plane permeability was higher compared to the through-thickness permeability. Song et al. [10] implemented a similar approach, for which they predicted the permeability tensor of a 3D braided textile, they also found that in-plane and through thickness permeability values were consistently higher than 2D fabrics. Several researchers worked on modeling permeability, Gebart et al. [11] proposed an analytical model for predicting permeability using fiber geometry. They derived Navier-Stokes based expressions for permeability of a unidirectional preform consisting parallel and ordered fibers. Brusckke et al. [12] introduced another predictive model for permeability of an idealized domain consisting of a regular array of cylinders. The limitation of the Gebart and Brusckke models was that the physical model used to describe the system did not capture all structural details of a real preform. The preforms used in LCM processes are mostly woven or stitched fiber bundles, referred to as tows or yarns, and their geometric arrangements are usually more complex than individual fibers.

In the scope of this study, a systematic approach was adopted to characterize the permeability of different 3D woven reinforcements. A complete experimental investigation of in-plane and through thickness permeability is presented. The effect of multiple cycle compaction on permeability was also investigated at one fiber volume fraction (V_f).

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Three different types of 3D reinforcements supplied by Sigmatex, UK were selected for characterization. It was expected that different architectures would exhibit different compaction and flow behaviour. The z-binder yarns in all architectures have different paths or orientations to hold the structure together, see Figure. 1. The preform details are presented in Table 1. Fabric A is an orthogonal fabric having eight layers of warp and 9 layers of weft fiber bundles. Every one in nine warp yarns, there is an interlacing weaver with the rest of the warp stuffers. Fabric B is a layer to layer with six weft layers and five warp layers being the interlacing yarns. Fabric C is an angle interlock having eight warp layers and nine weft layers. One in three warp yarns is an interlacing weaver with the rest of warp stuffers.

Fabric Type	Areal Weight (g/m ²)	Warp Layers	Weft Layers	Uncompressed V_f
Orthogonal (A)	3353	8	9	0.37
Layer to Layer (B)	3045	5	6	0.35
Angle Interlock (C)	3260	8	9	0.26

Table 1: Details of the 3D reinforcements.

Figure 1: Different 3D reinforcement architectures, (a) top views, (b) schematic of front view.

2.2 Experimental Setup

In-plane Permeability

The in-plane test fixture is shown in Figure 2a. It consists of a 300 mm x 300 mm square toughened glass plate fixed in an aluminum frame, sitting on a 300 kN MTS testing machine. A circular steel plate of 250 mm diameter was used as the top platen to compact the preform. The top plate consists of a 10 mm central injection hole drilled from the side through which test fluid is injected. A pressure transducer is connected to the top plate which measures the injection pressure. Hydraulic oil, Shell Tellus S2 M32, with a viscosity of 0.08 Pa.s at 23°C was used as test fluid. The test fluid was used instead of the resin to ensure that no curing occurs during the test. The test fluid is injected using a pressure pot connected to compressed air. A high definition 8MP camera was placed under the glass plate to record the flow front progression with time. Sufficient and appropriate lighting was ensured to get distinguishable flow front without any reflections. A PC with LabVIEW data acquisition software was used to record the injection pressure. A 10 mm hole was punched in the center of a 200 mm x 200 mm preform sample to ensure radial in-plane flow. The preform sample was then placed on the glass plate with the hole aligned with the hole in the top platen. A compressive pre-load was applied and the preform was compacted at 2 mm/s to a target fiber volume fraction (0.45, 0.50, 0.55 and 0.65). The extension was held constant to allow for stress relaxation for about 2 minutes. After this, the test fluid was injected at constant pressure at a range between 150 – 200 kPa. The data from the pressure transducer, MTS machine and camera was extracted for post processing. The flow front was detected using image processing toolbox from Matlab.

Through Thickness Permeability

Through-thickness permeability has been measured using an existing saturated flow measurement device developed at the University of Auckland [13] (see Figure 2b). The device is housed within a 200 kN Instron universal testing machine, allowing for accurate control of sample thickness, and the potential for simultaneous compressibility and permeability measurements. Samples are cut using a stamping press to a diameter of 130 mm, while the through-thickness flow area has a diameter of 100 mm. Once the sample is compressed to the initial thickness for flow measurements, a highly viscous grease is injected around the sample perimeter, sealing the edge of the sample under pressure. This

system eliminates edge effects, and allows for excess grease to be expelled when reducing sample thickness to achieve higher V_f . In this study, measurements were made at five fiber volume fractions for each sample. At each V_f , a series of increasing pressure drops are applied across the sample, and the resulting fluid flow rates measured. Pressure transducers are situated either side of the sample, and utilising a simple steady state 1D flow analysis, permeability is calculated from the pressure drop and flow rate data.

Target V_f values for each sample were 0.45, 0.50, 0.55, 0.60, and 0.65. The actual sample thickness was measured using two digital displacement sensors, allowing calculation of actual V_f values. At each V_f , five successively higher pressure drops were applied across the sample, in the range from 30 to 140 kPa. A Heavy-Medium mineral oil from Mobil DTE™ was used as the test fluid, the viscosity being previously characterised as a function of temperature. The temperature of the oil in the pressure pot was constantly measured (varying from 20.3 to 21.8 °C), which equates to viscosity range from 0.129 to 0.143 Pa.s.

Figure 2: (a) In-plane permeability fixture at Khalifa University, (b) Through-thickness permeability fixture at the University of Auckland.

3.0 Flow Analysis

The flow is modelled using Darcy's law and the continuity equation for incompressible fluids. For the in-plane flow, the solution was constructed applying a constant injection pressure boundary condition. The flow in all 3D reinforcements was anisotropic with elliptical flow fronts. Determination of principal in-plane permeability values K_{11} and K_{22} was based on measurement of the principal axes of the flow front ellipse as function of time. This technique is well documented by Weitzenbock et al. [14, 15] which calculates the permeability without prior knowledge of the orientation of principal axes. Equation 1 and 2 [15] was formulated after analysing the flow ellipse.

$$K_{11} = \frac{\mu\phi}{4t\Delta P} \left\{ x_f^2 \left[2 \ln \left(\frac{x_f}{x_o} - 1 \right) + x_o^2 \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

$$K_{22} = \frac{\mu\phi}{4t\Delta P} \left\{ y_f^2 \left[2 \ln \left(\frac{y}{y_o} - 1 \right) + y_o^2 \right] \right\} \quad (2)$$

where x_f and y_f are the coordinates of the flow front in the ellipse-axis referential system and x_0 and y_0 the dimension of the inlet hole. The porosity is defined by ϕ , t is the injection time and ΔP is the pressure difference between the injection point and the flow front. Equation 3 was used to obtain the through thickness permeability (K_{33}). The through thickness permeability was computed from the measured flow rate using Darcy's law;

$$K_{33} = \frac{Qh\mu}{A \cdot \Delta P} \quad (3)$$

where Q is the volumetric flow rate through the sample, h is the imposed cavity thickness, μ the fluid viscosity, A the area of imposed flow and ΔP the applied pressure differential.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 In-Plane Permeability

The permeability behavior of the different 3D materials tested is presented in Figure 3, showing the influence of preform architecture on the permeability. These tests were conducted to determine the principal permeability for a range of fiber volume fractions. Figure 4 presents photos of elliptic flow fronts in each fabric. The components of the in-plane permeability tensor are defined as the principal directions of the ellipse observed at the flow front. Often, these principal directions are different from the warp and weft directions. Figure 3 shows that permeability in warp direction was consistently higher than weft for all reinforcements tested, layer to layer had more differences between in-plane permeability values, as a result, flow was more elliptical. This permeability behavior was moderately different for angle interlock where the flow was closer to a circular pattern. Orthogonal preforms showed highest permeability in the weft direction at low V_f . This was due to large gaps present near to the z-binder yarns on the surface as shown in Figure 1. However, at higher V_f , and due to flattening of binder yarns, surface pore sizes reduced which resulted in reduced permeability. The permeability converged to the angle interlock permeability values at $V_f = 0.65$. For layer to layer, the surface pores that run through the thickness were less, hence slower in-plane flow was observed.

It is important to mention that the anisotropy ratio for the angle interlock and orthogonal materials remained nearly constant as seen in Figure 5, whereas, it increases for the layer to layer fabric. Possibly due to binder yarns that separate the tows under compression and restrict inter tow nesting. The flow is governed by gaps between tows, in layer to layer, upon compression; the pores between the tows disappear. The difference in flow behaviour in the weft and warp direction affects the anisotropy. The principal angle for orthogonal and layer to layer was between 0° and 1° . However, for angle interlock, it was approximately 0° at low V_f and approximately 3° to 3.8° clockwise at higher V_f . Hoes et al [16] showed that nesting between layers is the main source of permeability scatter which can be reduced by restricting the tow movement. In the studied 3D fabrics, the tow movement was restricted by the binder yarn, however, scatter was greater at low V_f . This can be explained by strong dependence of flow on accuracy of the punched hole (diameter and location) in the sample.

4.2 Through Thickness Permeability

The through-thickness permeability K_{33} was measured in saturated unidirectional flow experiments. The experimental values of K_{33} for all preforms are plotted in Figure 3 along with the in-plane permeability values. For layer to layer, the curve for K_{33} as a function of V_f was significantly less steep than for orthogonal and angle interlock. The figure also indicated that the drop in K_{33} with increasing V_f was more significant than for the in-plane values. The difference between K_{33} and K_{22} for

layer to layer was not significant. All permeability data was fitted using the following exponential function, with resulting model parameters shown in Table 2.

$$K(V_f) = A \cdot \exp(B \cdot V_f) \tag{4}$$

Direction	K_{11}		K_{22}		K_{33}	
	A	B	A	B	A	B
Orthogonal	2E-09	-6.62	3E-10	-6.09	3E-08	-15.41
Angle Interlock	4E-10	-4.55	3E-10	-4.86	2E-06	-23.67
Layer to Layer	2E-09	-7.94	3E-09	-12.22	3E-08	-16.78

Table 2: Model Parameters.

Figure 3: In-plane and through thickness permeability of 3D fabrics, (a) Orthogonal, (b) Angle Interlock, (c) Layer to Layer

Figure 4: Ellipse of wet fabric during in plane permeability characterization at $V_f = 65\%$, (a) Orthogonal, (b) Angle interlock, (c) Layer to layer.

Figure 5: In-plane anisotropy of the three fabric preforms K_{11}/K_{22}

4.3 Micrographs

To physically examine the microstructure before and after compaction, samples were sectioned and potted in epoxy resin. The internal microstructures of the samples were observed using an optical microscope. Two types of samples were prepared for each reinforcement, without compaction, and at 65% fiber volume fraction. Figure 6 presents micrographs of each type of sample. For orthogonal, it can be observed that reinforcement compaction reduced gaps between fiber tows, in addition, compaction also flattened and stretched the z-binder yarns at top and bottom surfaces while it bent and buckled in the vertical direction, resulting in more efficient packing of fibers which reduced open channels for resin flow, hence lower permeability was confirmed. Angle interlock had the least fiber volume fraction in the un-compressed state. Upon compression, the z-yarn flattened and bent. Observing layer to layer; the fiber tows flattened with ease in the plane which resulted in smallest pores among all fabrics; which resulted in significantly low permeability.

Figure 6: Micrographs of 3D composites (a-c) cross sections of uncompressed preforms, (d-f) cross sections of preforms at 65% fiber volume fraction.

4.4 Permeability after Multiple Cycle Compaction

Figure 7 shows in-plane permeability comparisons of single cycle and multiple cycle compacted preforms at $V_f = 0.65$. It was noted that cyclic loading had almost no effect on the layer to layer permeability. Whereas orthogonal and angle interlock preforms showed reduction by 7% and 37% in the weft and 23% and 54% in the warp direction respectively. Cyclic compaction imparts permanent deformation of tows which reduces open channels and induces more nesting of fiber bundles, hence lower preform permeability. The large reduction in permeability for angle interlock motivated another investigation which is underway for through thickness permeability after cyclic compaction.

Figure 7: Comparison between permeability of single and cyclic compaction preforms at 0.65 V_f (a) K_{11} , and (b) K_{22} .

5 CONCLUSIONS

A comprehensive set of experimental results on the permeability behaviour of 3D reinforcements was presented. Three different types of reinforcements were characterized for in-plane and through-thickness permeability. Experimental studies were carried out on orthogonal, layer to layer and angle interlock fabrics. An apparent dependence of permeability on the binder yarn existed in the 3D fabrics.

The binder yarns restrict movement of adjacent tows, and preserve flow anisotropy. At low fiber volume fraction, the in-plane permeability was highest for orthogonal. The cyclic loading/unloading or multiple cycle compaction of preforms produced more permanent deformation in the reinforcements causing lower in-plane permeability. The presented micrographs have confirmed that reinforcement's permanent deformation has been shown to be significant in all cases, causing flatness of the tows which reduces permeability significantly for orthogonal and angle interlock fabrics.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Mr. Jimmy Thomas, Mr. Bittu Scaria at Khalifa University for their assistance in conducting the experiments. The authors gratefully acknowledge Mubadala Aerospace and Khalifa University for providing the financial support for this research project.

REFERENCES

- [1] Tan, P., L. Tong, G. Steven, and T. Ishikawa (2000). Behavior of 3D orthogonal woven CFRP composites. Part I. Experimental investigation, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 31(3), pp. 259-271.
- [2] Tan, P., L. Tong, and G. Steven (2000). Behavior of 3D orthogonal woven CFRP composites. Part II. FEA and analytical modeling approaches, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 31(3), pp. 273-281.
- [3] Arbter, R., J. Beraud, C. Binetruy, L. Bizet, J. Bréard, S. ComasCardona, C. Demaria, A. Endruweit, P. Ermanni, F. Gommer. (2011). Experimental determination of the permeability of textiles: a benchmark exercise, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 42(9), pp. 1157-1168.
- [4] Lundström, T., R. Stenberg, R. Bergström, H. Partanen, and P. Birkeland (2000). In-plane permeability measurements: a nordic round robin study, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 31(1), pp. 29-43.
- [5] Parnas, R. S. and A. J. Salem (1993). A comparison of the unidirectional and radial in-plane flow of fluids through woven composite reinforcements, *Polymer Composites*, 14(5), pp. 383-394.
- [6] Parnas, R. S., K. M. Flynn, and M. E. Dal-Favero (1997). A permeability database for composites manufacturing, *Polymer Composites*, 18(5), pp. 623-633.
- [7] Endruweit, A. and A. Long (2010). Analysis of compressibility and permeability of selected 3D woven reinforcements, *Journal of composite materials*, 44(24), pp. 2833-2862.
- [8] Mohamed, M. k. k. Wetzel. (2006). 3D Woven Carbon/Glass Hybrid Spar Cap for Wind Turbine Rotor Blade. *Journal of Sol. Energy Eng.* 128(4), 562-573.
- [9] Ngo, N. and K. Tamma (2004). Complex three-dimensional microstructural permeability prediction of porous media with and without compaction, *International journal for numerical methods in engineering*, 60(10), pp. 1741-1757.

- [10] Song, Y., K. Chung, T. Kang, and J. Youn (2004). Prediction of permeability tensor for three dimensional circular braided preform by applying finite volume method to a unit cell, *Composites Science and Technology*, 64(10), pp. 1629-1636.
- [11] Gebart, B. (1992). Permeability of unidirectional reinforcements for RTM, *Journal of composite materials*, 26(8), pp. 1100-1133.
- [12] Brusckke, M. V. (1992) A predictive model for permeability and non-isothermal tow of viscous and shear-thinning fluids in anisotropic fibrous media, Ph.D. thesis, University of Delaware Center for Composite Materials.
- [13] Liotier, P. J., Govignon, Q., Swery, E., Drapier, S., and Bickerton, S. (2015). Characterisation of woven flax fibres reinforcements: Effect of the shear on the in-plane permeability. *Journal of Composite Materials*, DOI: 10.11177/0021998314565411.
- [14] Weitzenböck, J., R. Sheno, and P. Wilson (1999). Radial flow permeability measurement. Part A: Theory, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 30(6), pp. 781-796.
- [15] Weitzenböck, J., R. Sheno, and P. Wilson (1999). Radial flow permeability measurement. Part A: Application, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 30(6), pp. 781-796.
- [16] Hoes, K. D. Dinescu. H. Sol, R. S. Parnas, S. Lomov (2004). Study of nesting induced scatter of permeability values in layered reinforcement fabrics, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 35(12), pp. 1407-1418.